

Fig.2 Typical example of SEM images showing polymer droplets on a single BC nanofibre. (a) PLLA and (b) PLLA and RP1 (5 wt.-%).

Table 1. The wettability of the polymers, PLLA, RP1 and the blend, on BC nanofibrils.

Polymer	Contact angle (°)
PLLA	35.4 ± 1.6
PLLA-RP1	29.0 ± 2.7
RP1	14.9 ± 2.7

Table 2. The mechanical properties of BC (5 wt.-%) reinforced PLLA, with and without RP1 (5 wt.-%) as the compatibiliser.

Samples	E (GPa)	σ (MPa)
PLLA	4.08 ± 0.07	63.1 ± 2.0
RP1	3.74 ± 0.04	35.6 ± 1.9
PLLA-RP1 (5 wt.-%)	3.75 ± 0.05	56.1 ± 1.1
PLLA-BC (5 wt.-%)	4.55 ± 0.03	57.8 ± 5.9
RP1-BC (5 wt.-%)	4.33 ± 0.09	51.9 ± 0.5
PLLA-RP1 (4.75 wt.-%)-BC (5 wt.-%)	4.71 ± 0.13	67.4 ± 1.1

E and σ denote the Young's modulus and tensile strength, respectively.

Tensile tests showed that RP1 has a lower Young's modulus and lower tensile strength than PLLA. Its lower stiffness and strength are likely due to this reduction in crystallinity, presumably caused by the two acetyl substituents. Blending 5 wt.-% RP1 with PLLA resulted in a reduction of the tensile strength of the blend, which decreased by 12% from 63.1 MPa to 56.1 MPa. As expected, the incorporation of the stiff BC (5 wt.-%) into PLLA resulted in a higher Young's modulus compared to PLLA, increasing by 12% (from 4.08 GPa to 4.55 GPa). The rule-of-mixtures for composite materials predicts that the introduction of a stiff filler/reinforcement (in this case, the stiff BC nanofibres) into a softer polymer matrix (in this case, PLLA) will improve the Young's modulus of the composite. However, the tensile strength of the PLLA-BC (5 wt.-%) nanocomposite decreased by 10%, from 63.1 MPa for PLLA to 57.8 MPa. This is consistent with our previous findings and is a result of insufficient interfacial adhesion between BC nanofibrils and PLLA. When BC nanofibres were used as filler (5 wt.-%) for RP1, the Young's modulus of the

resulting nanocomposites increased from 3.74 GPa to 4.33 GPa (table 2). It is important to note that the tensile strength of the RP1-BC nanocomposite also improved from 35.6 MPa to almost 52 MPa. This improvement is attributed to the better affinity between BC nanofibrils and RP1, which enables efficient transfer of stress from the matrix to the reinforcing nanofibres. The direct wetting measurements corroborate the tensile properties of the nanocomposites (see table 1).

3. Conclusions

In conclusion, we reported the use of a bio-derived PLLA copolymer (RP1) as a compatibilising agent to produce BC reinforced PLLA nanocomposites with high stiffness and strength. The preparation of BC-PLLA nanocomposites, using 5 wt.-% RP1 as the compatibiliser, resulted in an improvement of both the Young's modulus (15% higher) and the tensile strength (7% higher) compared to the PLLA-BC composite. BC nanocomposites with high BC loading of 60 vol.-% was also manufactured. A Young's modulus and tensile strength of 6.5 GPa and 125 MPa were achieved, respectively (results not shown). The bio-derived copolymer enables enhanced fibre-matrix stress transfer leading to better performance. The approach is completely different to the conventional use of petrochemically derived compatibilisers, such as maleic anhydride grafted PLA, and highlights the potential to use bio-derived polymers to prepare fully renewable composite materials.

References

- [1] K.Y. Lee, J.J. Blaker, A. Bismarck "Surface functionalization of bacterial cellulose as the route to produce green polylactide nanocomposites with improved properties" *Comp. Sci. Tech.* 2009, 69, 2724.
- [2] B. Braun, J.R. Dorgan, "Single-step method for the isolation and surface functionalization of cellulosic nanowhiskers" *Biomacromolecules* 2009, 10, 334.
- [3] H.S. Kim, B.H. Lee, S. Lee, H.J. Kim, J. Dorgan "Enhanced interfacial adhesion, mechanical and thermal properties of natural flour-filled biodegradable polymer bio-composites" *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim* 2011, 104, 331.
- [4] M. Tang, A.J.P. White, M.M. Stevens, C.K. Williams "Biomaterials from sugars: ring-opening polymerization of carbohydrate lactone" *Chem. Comm.* 2009, 8, 941.